

EFFECTS OF IRRIGATION REGIMES AND CROP ROTATION ON BULK SOIL MASS

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Abstract. This article presents the results of studies on the effects of short-row and crop rotation, deep tillage on soil bulk density between the rows of cotton.

Keywords: cotton, experiment, cropping systems, irrigation, short-row.

Before studying the effects of short rotation cropping systems, irrigation regimes and different rates of mineral fertilizers on soil bulk density in field experiment 3, it was found to be 1.274 h/cm³ in the 0-30 cm layer and 1.418 h/cm³ in the 30-50 cm layer. (Table 1). This is considered optimal for the growth and development of any plant.

Table 1

Experiment 3 Volumetric mass and porosity of the soil at the beginning of the period of operation

Soil layer, cm	Density, g/cm ³
0-10	1,242
10-20	1,265
20-30	1,315
0-30	1,274
30-40	1,361
40-50	1,476
30-50	1,418
50-60	1,472
60-70	1,463
70-80	1,419
80-90	1,415
90-100	1,362
40-100	1,435
0-100	1,379

It was observed that the volume mass of the soil was different according to the options under the influence of the applied factors towards the end of the cotton period. In the 70-70-60% irrigation regime of the short-row rotation 1:1, winter wheat: cotton system, when mineral fertilizers were applied at the rate of N₁₆₀P₁₁₂K₈₀ kg/ha, the volume mass of the soil in the 0-30 cm layer was 1,328 g/cm³, 30-50 cm layer was found to be 1.452 g/cm³. In this crop rotation system, when mineral fertilizers N₂₀₀P₁₄₀K₁₀₀ and N₂₄₀P₁₆₈K₁₂₀ kg/ha were applied, the volume mass of the soil in the 0-30 cm layer decreased by 0.003-0.007 h/cm³ compared to option 1. was noted that the volume mass of the soil was 0.006-0.013 h/cm³ in the 30-50 cm layer (Table 2).

In the 1:1 winter wheat: cotton system of short rotation, it was observed that the volume mass of the soil increased due to the increase of the irrigation regime when the irrigation regime was 70-75-65% compared to the irrigation regime of 70-70-60%. The volume mass of the soil in

the 0-30 cm layer in the 4-5-6 options with the irrigation mode of 70-75-65% compared to the 1-2-3 options with the irrigation mode of 70-70-60% is 0.021-0.022-0.024 g/ It was found that it increased compared to cm³. In the 1:1 winter wheat: cotton system of short-row rotation, the most positive volume mass of the soil was recorded in option 3 (1,321-1,439 g/cm³) where mineral fertilizers were applied at the rate of N₂₄₀P₁₆₈K₁₂₀ kg/ha in the regime of 70-70-60% irrigation.

Table 2

Experiment 3 soil bulk density and porosity

Var no	Short rotation cropping systems	Irrigation pattern of cotton in relation to BdFMC, %	Standards of mineral fertilizers used in cotton, kg/ha	Soil layer, cm	Volumetric mass of soil, g/cm ³
1	1:1, winter wheat: cotton	70-70-60 %	N ₁₆₀ P ₁₁₂ K ₈₀	0-30	1,328
				30-50	1,452
2			N ₂₀₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₁₀₀	0-30	1,325
				30-50	1,446
3			N ₂₄₀ P ₁₆₈ K ₁₂₀	0-30	1,321
				30-50	1,439
4		70-75-65 %	N ₁₆₀ P ₁₁₂ K ₈₀	0-30	1,349
				30-50	1,457
5			N ₂₀₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₁₀₀	0-30	1,347
				30-50	1,452
6			N ₂₄₀ P ₁₆₈ K ₁₂₀	0-30	1,345
				30-50	1,449
7	1:1, winter wheat+repeated crop soybean: cotton	70-70-60 %	N ₁₆₀ P ₁₁₂ K ₈₀	0-30	1,326
				30-50	1,445
8			N ₂₀₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₁₀₀	0-30	1,323
				30-50	1,443
9			N ₂₄₀ P ₁₆₈ K ₁₂₀	0-30	1,320
				30-50	1,443
10		70-75-65 %	N ₁₆₀ P ₁₁₂ K ₈₀	0-30	1,347
				30-50	1,456
11			N ₂₀₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₁₀₀	0-30	1,344
				30-50	1,450
12			N ₂₄₀ P ₁₆₈ K ₁₂₀	0-30	1,339
				30-50	1,448
13	1:1, winter wheat+repeated crop soybean+mixed siderate crops (oats, blue peas, rapeseed):cotton	70-70-60 %	N ₁₆₀ P ₁₁₂ K ₈₀	0-30	1,319
				30-50	1,436
14			N ₂₀₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₁₀₀	0-30	1,317
				30-50	1,434
15			N ₂₄₀ P ₁₆₈ K ₁₂₀	0-30	1,314
				30-50	1,431
16		70-75-65 %	N ₁₆₀ P ₁₁₂ K ₈₀	0-30	1,325
				30-50	1,445

17			N ₂₀₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₁₀₀	0-30	1,322
				30-50	1,442
18			N ₂₄₀ P ₁₆₈ K ₁₂₀	0-30	1,320
				30-50	1,435

When analyzing the data obtained from the field experiments, the volume mass of the soil in the options planted in the 1:1 short-row rotation, winter wheat-repeated crop soybean:cotton system compared to the options planted in the short-row rotation 1:1, winter wheat:cotton, the leguminous crop soybean and from it was found that it was better due to the amount of remaining root residues. 7-8 of the short repeated crop 1:1, winter wheat+repeated crop soybean: cotton, the irrigation regime was 70-70-60%, mineral fertilizers were applied at the rates of N₁₆₀P₁₁₂K₈₀ kg/ha, N₂₀₀P₁₄₀K₁₀₀ kg/ha and N₂₄₀P₁₆₈K₁₂₀ kg/ha. In options 9, 1:1 short-rotation, winter wheat:cotton system, mineral fertilizers N₁₆₀P₁₁₂K₈₀ kg/ha,

According to the results of field experiments, short-row rotation 1:1, winter wheat + repeated crop soybean: cotton system was used, 70-75-65% irrigation regime in 10-11-12 variants 0-30 according to the increase of mineral fertilizers. In the cm layer, the volume mass of the soil was 1,347-1,344-1,339 g/cm³, and in the 30-50 cm layer, the volume mass of the soil was 1,456-1,450-1,448 g/cm³, respectively. It was found that the best volume mass of soil in the agro background where this crop rotation system was used was option 12, and its volume mass was 1.339 g/cm³ in the 0-30 cm soil layer, and 1.448 g/cm³ in the 30-50 cm layer.

Analyzing the results obtained from the field experiments, 1:1 short rotation, winter wheat+repeated soybean+mixed intercrops (oats, green peas, rapeseed):cotton planted with 70-70-65% irrigation regime was used 13-14-15- it was noted that the volume mass of the soil was 0.009-0.008-0.007 g/cm³ less than the control options planted in the 1:1 winter wheat: cotton system, and 0.016-0.012-0.008 g/cm³ in the 30-50 cm layer. In this crop rotation system, in options 16-17-18, where the irrigation regime is increased to 70-75-65%, the 1:1 short-row rotation, winter wheat: cotton system is 0.003-0.003-0.003-0.003- 0.001 g/cm³ and 0.024-0.025-0.025 g/cm³ were positive compared to 70-75-65% irrigation regime.

The results of the analysis carried out in the experiment showed that the volume mass of the soil by the end of the operation period achieved the best results in the short-row rotation 1:1, winter wheat + repeated crop soybean + mixed intermediate crops (oats, blue peas, rapeseed): cotton planted, 70- It was observed in option 15, which was irrigated in 70-65% irrigation mode, mineral fertilizers were applied at the rate of N₂₄₀P₁₆₈K₁₂₀ kg/ha. In this option, the volume mass of the soil was 1.314 g/cm³ in the 0-30 cm layer, and 1.431 g/cm³ in the 30-50 cm soil layer, and this indicator was at the beginning of the application period.1.274-1.418 g/cm³, and in the 1st option, which was calculated as control, it was 1.328-1.452 g/cm³.

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